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**CONSTRUCTIVIST CLASSROOM
ROLE OF TECHNOLOGY**

**SELF-CONFIDENCE &
ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT**

**STUDY CHEMISTRY
FOR PLEASURE**

**HIGHER EDUCATION
STUDENTS' SATISFACTION**

**SCIENCE CURRICULUM
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**INFLUENCE OF ATTITUDE
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**CHALLENGES OF
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Satisfaction of North-East Students in the Higher Educational Institutions of Delhi National Capital Region

Most of the quality definitions are consumer-centered. Now, education is being considered as a consumer good. A student is one of the consumers of education. So, their satisfaction is of utmost importance. This paper was an attempt to study the satisfaction of North-East students, studying in Delhi National Capital Region (NCR) from the facilities and the services of their respective institutions. The sample of the study comprised 80 students (40 boys and 40 girls) selected through purposive sampling technique. For the data collection Students Institution Satisfaction Scale [SISS-ASJS] (2013) developed by Prof. Sohrab Ali and Dr. Sanjeev Kumar Jha was used. For analysis and interpretation, statistical techniques like Mean, Standard Deviation, and t-test were employed. The paper concluded that North-East students have moderate level of satisfaction from the facilities and the services of their respective institutions in Delhi NCR. The analysis further showed that the type of institution i.e. public or private, gender i.e. boy or girl, and stream of study i.e. academic or professional has no effect on students satisfaction.

North-East in India comprises eight States. The States are Assam, Arunachal Pradesh, Manipur, Meghalaya, Mizoram, Nagaland, Sikkim and Tripura. The literacy rate of North-East states is 70.04 percent with a total population of 40 million (Census, 2011), which is close to the national literacy rate (74.04 per cent). However, the status at higher level is different in this region as compared to the rest of the country.

The higher education system in the region was growing slowly up to last decade. The region got its first university in 1948 at Guwahati, Assam. But this decade is witnessing a rapid growth in higher education system in this region. As of 2015, the region had 51 universities, including 10 central, 12 state, 28 private and 1 privately-sponsored deemed to be universities. (www.ugc.ac.in, 2015). Now the region claims better statistics in terms of number of universities for its habitants compared to other parts of the country. The region has one university for 800000 habitants whereas in India one university

serves 1700000 habitants (authors' calculation).

Despite this fact, a large number of students migrate to metro cities every year, including Delhi in search of better higher education. A significant number of students come to Delhi national capital region (NCR) to get higher education. According to Tiakala (2013) the main reasons for this from Nagaland are "availability of better study materials, broader outlook for grasping diversified knowledge, competitive environment, learning environment for better career prospects".

Student's Satisfaction

Education is one of the 12 tradable goods in the World Trade Organization (WTO). According to Patnaik (2013) "there would be little disagreement over the fact that there has been a universal tendency in the recent period to 'commoditize' education, to see centers of education as places where students come as 'buyers' to purchase this commodity, called education, at prices that increasingly reflect the earning capacity which the possession of this commodity gives them".

Applying the consumer behavior theory in education, we can regard students as consumers purchasing the services provided by education (Clare, 2004). The consumer is the top priority in consumer behavior theory. Thus, Student's Satisfaction should have the top priority in the educational institutions.

In order to take students' feedback their satisfaction level can be measured. Arokiasamy and Abdullah (2012) clearly pointed out that "student satisfaction assessment is vital in determining service quality at higher learning institutions".

The fulfillment or gratification of a desire, need, or appetite may be termed as satisfaction. Students' satisfaction is understood as a special form of customer satisfaction and

Dr. Sanjeev Kumar Jha is Project Consultant, National University of Educational Planning and Administration (NUEPA), New Delhi.
Tiakala is Ph.D. Research Scholar, Department of Teachers Training and Non-Formal Education (LASE), F/O Education Jamia Millia Islamia, New Delhi.

comprises five different categories curriculum, teachers, facilities, student's life and support (Kruger, 2009).

Most quality definitions are customer-centered and customer satisfaction is viewed as a function of perceived quality (Woo, 2006). Product specification is actually the minimum condition for quality, but not the sufficient condition. The sufficient condition is customer satisfaction and beyond (Mukhopadhyay, 2005). Ali and Jha (2013) state "if any university/institution claims that their university/institution has quality in its education because of university/institution has excellent infrastructure, faculty, curriculum, etc. it is an insufficient base for their claim. If they access Student's Satisfaction and if it is found to be very high, then the university/institution has quality in its education". The students have the right to obtain the best quality education (Chua, 2004). So, the Student's Satisfaction (SS) is a significant characteristic of quality education at the higher educational institutions. Jha and Ali (2014) suggested that "students' satisfaction should be at focus in the educational institution as most of quality definitions are consumer-centered".

Thus, students' satisfaction is a special form of customer satisfaction. In student's perspective fulfillment of expectations regarding educational facilities and services of students that is essential for their development may be termed as Student's Satisfaction.

The facilities and services required by the students comprise five categories i.e. tangibility (physical environment, facilities, equipments, etc.), reliability (consistency between promise and service), responsiveness (willing to help students and provide them prompt service), assurance (competency of university teaching and non-teaching staff) and empathy (caring and individual attention of

students (guidance and counseling cell)).

Justification of the Study

The construct of quality as conceptualized in the services literature is based on the perceived quality. As students are the direct recipients of the facilities and the services of the university, they can well judge the quality of education in their respective institutions. The recipient perspective is important to ensure the quality in higher education. Students can be the best judges to assess the quality of education as they are recipients of the facilities and the services. If an institution has satisfied students then it can be said that the institution has quality in its education.

It is important to study student's satisfaction as it is a significant characteristic of quality education at the higher educational institutions. Secondly, the students came to Delhi NCR in the quest of quality education.

One of the questions pertaining to their expectation is whether North-East students are satisfied with the quality of education or not. The study made an attempt to understand and get empirical evidences for it.

Operational Definitions

Student's Satisfaction (SS): Fulfillment of expectations regarding educational facilities and services of the university/ institution.

North-East Students: Students belonging to eight North-East States of India (namely Assam, Arunchal Pradesh, Manipur, Meghalaya, Mizoram, Nagaland, Sikkim and Tripura).

Objectives of the Study

- To study Students Satisfaction among students of Delhi NCR.
- To compare Students Satisfaction between students of public and private institutions.
- To compare Students Satisfaction between boys and girl students.
- To compare Students Satisfaction between academic and professional stream students.

Hypotheses of the Study

- ◆ There is high satisfaction among students, studying in Delhi NCR
- ◆ There is no significant difference in Students Satisfaction between students of public and private institutions.
- ◆ There is no significant difference in Students Satisfaction between boys and girls students.
- ◆ There is no significant difference in Students Satisfaction between academic and professional stream students.

Methodology

Survey Method was employed for the study. Primary data source was used for the study.

Population

Population comprised "all the North-East students, studying in higher educational institutions of Delhi NCR.

Sample

The sample of the study was 80 (40 boys and 40 girls) North-East students studying in institutions of higher education in Delhi NCR

Figure-1: Research Design

selected through the use of 'Purposive Sampling Technique'.

Eighty students comprised 40 boys (21 from academic and 17 from professional streams) and 40 girls (24 from academics and 16 from professional streams).

Tool Used

Students' Institution Satisfaction Scale (SISS-ASJS, 2013) (developed by Prof. Sohrab Ali and Dr. Sanjeev Kumar Jha) was used for data collection. The tool has five dimensions namely tangibility, reliability, responsiveness, assurance and empathy with 47 items and it has very high validity and reliability.

Statistical Techniques

Statistical techniques like Mean, Standard Deviation, and t-test were employed.

Analysis and Interpretation

Objective 1

Student's Satisfaction

Boys and girls have a moderate level of satisfaction (as per Z-score norms of the SISS-AJ, 2013) with the

facilities and the services of their respective institutions. Furthermore, overall, students are also moderately satisfied (as per Z-score norms of the SISS-AJ, 2013) with the facilities and the services of their respective institutions.

Objective 2

Comparison of Students Satisfaction between students of public and private institutions

The t-test was not significant ($p > .05$, Table 2) between public and private university students. Thus, null hypothesis H_0 , "there is no significant difference in Students Satisfaction between students of public and private institutions" is accepted. So, the type of institution has no relation with Student's Satisfaction.

However, students of both types of the institutions have moderate level of satisfaction (as per Z-score norms of the SISS-AJ, 2013).

Objective 3

Comparison of Students Satisfaction between boys and girls students

The t-test was not significant ($p > .05$, Table 3) between public and private university students. Thus, null hypothesis H_0 , "there is no significant difference in Students Satisfaction between boys and girls students" is accepted. So, gender of the students has no relation with their satisfaction. The finding is in consonance with the findings of Jha and Ali (2014), & Kumar and Phogat (2014).

However, boys and girls have moderate level of satisfaction (as per Z-score norms of the SISS-AJ, 2013).

Objective 4

Comparison of Students Satisfaction between academic and professional students

The t-test was not significant ($p > .05$, Table 4) between academic and professional stream students. Thus, the null hypothesis H_0 , "there is no significant difference in Students Satisfaction between academic and professional stream students" is accepted. So, the stream of students has no relation with their satisfaction.

However, academic and professional stream students have moderate level of satisfaction (as per Z-score norms of the SISS-AJ, 2013).

Conclusion

Students Satisfaction can be used as an instrument to assure quality in educational institutions. The regular assessment of students' satisfaction can help institutions to understand their strengths and weaknesses. It will not only be helpful in fulfilling the needs of the students but also helps in developing the institution as world class institutions.

It may further be concluded that the higher educational institutions of metro cities attract students from different regions of India as many students come in search of a quality higher education in (public and private) institutions of Delhi NCR. It was found that students have

Table-1: Description of Students' Satisfaction

Group	Number	Range	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Boy	40	82	111	193	164.17	21.83
Girl	40	75	121	196	171.73	20.32
Total	80	85	111	196	168.17	21.271

Table-2: Students Satisfaction of Public and Private Institutions

Sl.No.	Institution	Number	Mean	SD	SE _M	t-ratio	p	Sig.
1.	Public	46	171.70	20.27	2.9	1.74	.08	NS
2.	Private	34	163.41	22.01	3.7			

NS-Not Significant

Table-3: Students Satisfaction of Boys and Girls

Sl.No.	Gender	Number	Mean	SD	SE _M	t-ratio	p	Sig.
1.	Boy	40	164.63	21.83	3.4	1.50	0.13	NS
2.	Girl	40	171.73	20.34	3.2			

NS-Not Significant

Table-4: Students Satisfaction of Academic and Professional Stream Students

Sl.No.	Stream	Number	Mean	SD	SE _M	t-ratio	p	Sig.
1.	Academic	47	166.87	20.41	2.9	0.65	0.51	NS
2.	Professional	33	170.03	22.62	3.9			

moderate level of satisfaction with the facilities and the services of the institutions. Moreover, Students' Satisfaction is irrespective of type of institution i.e. public or private, gender of student i.e. boy or girl, and stream of study i.e. academic or professional. This implies if an institution manages a common set of facilities and services then it will fulfill needs of all the students.

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